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Annotation: In this article reflects the views of the accomplished critic and literary scholar Ozod Sharafiddinov about Abdulhamid Chulpan. Ozad Sharafiddinov reacts to the opinions of literary scholars who evaluated Chulpan's work in his time and compares with other articles. Comparative-typological, sociological analysis methods were used in writing the article.

Key words: period, environment, criticism, literary studies, modernity, analysis, poetry, new Uzbek literature.

INTRODUCTION

Ozod Sharafiddinov has a special place in Uzbek literature criticism in the second half of the 20th century. The scientist made a great contribution to Uzbek literary studies with his literary and aesthetic views. Ozod Sharafiddinov dealt with the problems of poetry, wrote literary and critical articles about Uzbek poetry and its situation. Scientific-creative, literary-critical researches of that period "Zamon. Kalb. Poezia" (1962). The scientist created literary portraits about the representatives of Uzbek literature, such as Oybek, Gafur Gulam, Abdulla Qahhor, Sheikhzoda, Mirtemir, Zulfiya: "Istedod jilolari" (1976), "Adabiy etyudlar" (1968), "Abdulla Qahhor" (1988), "Birinchi mo'jiza" " (1979). The book of literary and critical essays "Yalovbardarlar" (1974) about the works of world literature figures occupies an important place in the work of Ozod Sharafiddinov. Ozod Sharafiddinov describes the situations in the Uzbek literary process from the 60s of the 20th century to the 19th century in "Talant - khalk mulki" (1979), "Adabiyot- hayot darsligi" (1981), "Guzallik izlab" (1985), "Haqiqatga sadoqat" (1988), He reflected in his

works such as "Sardaftar sahiflari" (1999), "President" (2003). In the 60s and 80s of the 20th century, Ozod Sharafiddinov tried to devoted to learn the life and work of Chulpan. During the years of independence, Ozod Sharafiddinov did great work as a literary critic, translator, and public figure. The critic's aesthetic principles are reflected in the books "Chulpon" (1991), "Chulpanni anglash" (1994), "E'tiqodimni nega o'zgartirdim" (1997). In the following years, Ozod Sharafiddinov wrote dozens of articles about Uzbek writers, cultural and artistic figures, and scientists. Especially during the years of independence, the scientist was seriously engaged in the work of Chulpan. In the book " Chulpanni anglash", he gave an impartial assessment of the poet's work. Literary critic Chulpon began his work in 1914, and admits that in 1920-1927 his work boiled like a spring, and even overflowed. The scientist also notes that some literary critics from abroad evaluated Chulpon's work sincerely. In our opinion, the thing that tormented Ozod Sharafiddinov is that Chulpon's work was not given a sufficiently objective assessment during his time and even after. The scientist writes in the book "Chulpanni anglash": "... the poet has been condemned for almost seventy years. During this period, there were no slanders left unsaid to the honor of the poet. In hundreds of articles, books, and lectures, he was called a "bourgeois poet", "modernist", "ideologically corrupt", "enemies singer", "nationalist", "counter-revolutionary", "a vassal who did not understand the October Revolution", "an alien element that poisons the minds of young people". "Enemy of the people" and another curses were added. Not for one year, not for ten years, for seventy years!" [1;28].

Ozod Sharafiddinov was sorrowful that Chulpan's works was not perceived clearly for seventy years. Because the socio-political events at that time did not allow it. The scholar does not sharpen the idea that no one has learned the work of the poet for this seventy years and lists the scholars who have studied the Chulpan's creation through an ideology. In addition to the leader of the Uzbek immigrants , Boymirza Khayit, one of the Uzbek immigrants, have expressed a very high idea of

Chulpan, who was staying in Berlin in 20 years. But all these scholars stand up and wrote the work of the Chulpan and wrote articles. True, there was a large wall between that socialist period and the atmosphere in another country. Ozod Sharafiddinov does not judge to understand Chulpan, but said that the socialist ideology had led to this understanding of the art poet.

Ozod Sharafiddinov, a scientist who studied the works of Chulpan, chronologically expressed the opinions expressed by the poet and those who expressed them. In particular, Tatarstan scientist Zarif Bashariy was the first to comment on Chulpan's work in the press, Ozod Sharafiddinov noted. He writes: "On May 4, 1923, Zarif Bashari published a description of Chulpan's first collection, "Uygonish", in the "Turkistan" newspaper. At the very beginning of the review, "Chulpan is one of the earliest examples of Uzbek poets of the later period and worthy of being called a poet in the true sense of the word. it's okay" he said, and then he mentions "Chulpan friend's true heart and feeling poet", that is, his sensitive lyricism, and gives examples that provoke this idea. With the help of a critical poem, it helps to add imagery, depth of feelings, and words to Chulpan's.

Another critic, Vadud Mahmud, also notes that he wrote the preface to Chulpan's poetry collection "Buloklar" and analyzed his poem "Amalning o'limi". The scientist adds that Vadud Mahmud allows himself to be a narcissist, but he has penetrated far into the essence of Chulpan's poetry. Ozod Sharafiddinov also specially acknowledges scientist Abdurahman Sa'di, who studied Chulpan's work from a different perspective. For example, in 1924, in two issues of the "Zarafshon" newspaper, with two articles "Uzbek yosh shoirlari" and "Chulpan", he noted that he had thoroughly investigated Chulpan's work, and Ozod Sharafiddinov in the book "Understanding Chulpan". Abdurahman Sa'di describes Chulpan as "he burns and burns". Ozod Sharafiddinov says that this definition is a proof that Chulpan is a "lyrical poet". The article also reveals with evidence that Chulpan is "a truly romantic heart poet (lyricist)".

In general, literary scholar Ozod Sharafiddinov emphasizes that understanding and studying Chulpan is relevant for today. The fact that scholar Chulpan allowed impartiality, correctness, and justice in illuminating his personality, and that he showed zeal for the will of the nation, the development of the nation, and the freedom of freedom in his poems and critical views, is of great importance in the development of modern literature and criticism.

Also, Ozad Sharafiddinov pays special attention to the slapdash-like foreword written by Abdulla Qadiri to Chulpan's book "Tong Sirlari". "Abdullah Qadiri rejects the slanders made in the press in honor of Chulpan, saying that "Chulpan's cry is a poet", although there are many tears in the poet's poems, Chulpan says that he "wants to collect smallpox from them". Munaqqid explains the common feature of the first articles about Chulpan by the fact that they tried to objectively check and evaluate the poet's work. In addition, in addition to the strengths of Chulpan, the articles also reflect on its weaknesses. In two articles, exactly one "defect" is visible, and this defect will later become the basis for completely condemning Chulpan's work, Ozod Sharafiddinov thinks, and quotes an excerpt from the article: "Zarif Bashiri writes: "The more Chulpan writes the words "people" and "community", the more even if he speaks, he is not a folk poet. He is a poet of intellectuals who are close to the people. There is very little nationalism in his style and spirit." Abdurrahman Saadi, who published an article a year later, reacts by saying: "Chulpan is not a poet of the masses, but a poet of the educated and intellectuals." The critic stated that in 1923-1924, the "accusation" that "the poet of the intellectuals, not the people's poet" was not accepted politically, and these "accusations" did not make much noise. Later, these "accusations" - being "not a poet of the people, but a poet of intellectuals" lead Chulpan to his death. Ozod Sharafiddinov, these reviews and articles did not fully reveal the poet's creativity, on the contrary, they were only one step of the huge staircase leading to the height of Chulpan. [1;37].

According to the critic, these stairs could have gone even higher, but they did not. Movements in the realization of the Chulpan went back, not forward. On February 14, 1927, an article titled "Uzbek Poets Chulpan" was published in the "Kizil Uzbekistan" newspaper with the signature of Ain (Olim Sharafiddinov). With this article, it was announced that the debate about Chulpan has started, says Ozod Sharafiddinov. After that, Aybek's "Chulpan. How to check the poet?! wrote an answer to Oybek with his article in favor of Chulpan's work and Usmankhan's article "Munaqqidning munaqqidi" against him. The scientist consistently analyzes the worldview of the scholars who have analyzed Chulpan's work and his poems, based on the unwritten laws of the ruling ideology. In particular, in 1927, literary critic Olim Sharafiddinov, who took the pseudonym Ain, started the inappropriate work of turning literature into a servant of the ruling ideology, and everything changed after he put on the glasses of classism, Ozod Sharafiddinov concludes. The scientist jokingly says, "Who proved when and where the poet of intellectuals cannot be a poet of the people?" Also, the critic notes that Akmal Ikramov, the First Secretary of the Central Committee of the Communist Party of Uzbekistan at that time, expressed his opinion on Chulpan's work and almost solved the issue: "We had a number of discussions on the pretext of Ayn's article about Chulpan's work. Ain Chulpan rightly emphasized the ideological instability of his work. I do not dare to speak about the literary value of this review. I will only repeat that there is no doubt that such healthy criticism is necessary in the field of ideology." In particular, Ozod Sharafiddinov admits that literary critics of that time praised the language of Ain Chulpan: "Today's Uzbek literary language is undoubtedly the language of Chulpan. The whole literary youth recognizes his language as an example. He imitates him." Later, Ain Chulpan is accused of being a dreamer. At the same time, the scientist criticizes Miyonbuzruk's opinions about Chulpan's drama "Yorkinoy" [1;23.]

Ozod Sharafiddinov analyzes every word of the article of the scientists who commented on the work of Chulpan. According to the critic, they also want to turn

Chulpan into a poet who serves the era like them. Also, behind the threats directed at Chulpan, there was a reference to other creators, the scientist concludes. Because the ruling representatives of that time want to give a lesson to the rest of them on the example of Chulpan, they want to return their martyrdom. The critic evaluates this phenomenon as "the transformation of literary studies and criticism into "manqurt."

Only in recent years Sh.Turdiyev, N.Karimov, B.Dostkaraev, M.Olimov, U.Dolimov, Z.Eshonova, D.Kuronov, U.Sultonov with the action of literary critics such as Chulpan's literary and critical works published before and after the revolution, which are now almost impossible to find, scattered in magazines and newspapers, began to enter scientific circulation, the critic writes in the article "Adabiyot yashasa - -millat yashar".

Ozod Sharafiddinov deeply explained the lyrical heritage of Chulpan, the mentality of "a poet with extraordinary talent", the individual, poetic, journalistic and socio-aesthetic nature of his poetry. Professor Bahadir Karimov writes about the scientist: [2;4] "Ozod Sharafiddinov had the tolerance and courage typical of great scientists." Not everyone is capable of self-examination, even if they have a flaw like a seed. Especially at a time when worldviews are changing, a person must first of all be brave enough to ask himself the question, "Why did I change my faith?" Acknowledging the truth of the ideas written in his scientific articles or books, which seemed correct at the time, and which have changed over time, is also a characteristic characteristic of a truly generous scientist. Looking at the work of Ozad Aka, it is obvious that there are places worthy of such an example. In particular, in the article "Adabiyot yashasa — millat yashar" Chulpan's article "Shura government and sanoe nafisa" as evidence of the poet's "positive reception of the revolution" and the assumption that it is a work "written under the influence of some works" of the "genius" after getting acquainted with new sources and he clearly writes that he has changed his mind." To analyze Chulpan's work, one must have the thinking and courage of a poet.

Ozod Sharafiddinov had such courage. Literary connoisseurs know that Ulug'bek Hamdam, a scholar of literature and writer, showed zeal in publishing the novel "Balance". In a word, Ozod Sharafidinov tries to show that the "unexplored reserve lands of literature" are actually flower gardens with the courage of criticism. In this sense, the books "Chulpan", " Chulpanni anglash", and "Adabiyot yashasa - millat yashar" were created as results of studying Chulpan's work based on new principles.

Ozod Sharafiddinov comments on Chulpan's article "Ulug' Hindi" published in the joint issue of "Maarif va uqituvchi" magazine dated 7-8, 1925. In this article, Chulpan presents his thoughts on the direction of the development of Uzbek literature on the pretext of Tagore. In what way does Chulpan consider Tagore's work to be an ideal work? It is important to note that when Chulpan expresses his opinion, he does not mean only Uzbek literature or Uzbek writers, but in general he means the young people of the East who entered the literature of the new literature at the beginning of the 20th century. According to Chulpan, these young people are suffering from "pathlessness". Besides, Chulpan himself suffers a lot from the pain of "lack of road". Why? How should we understand the term "disadvantage"? Chulpan writes: "Standing between the old literature and the new literature, the youth of the East is in a really awkward situation. The old literature is sweet: the new one is sweeter: the western one is even sweeter. Which one should be given more? Unfortunately, Chulpan does not say here what the "sweetness" of old and new literature is, but throughout the article he says that the pathlessness of young people is "in the beginning he is without a path" and points to its essence: "Let me talk a little about my own pathlessness: Navoi, Lutfiy, Boykara, Mashrab , Umar Khan, Fazli, Furqat, I read Muqimi: the same, the same, the same... The heart is looking for something else. I read Botu, Ghairatiy, Altay, Oybek, Julkunboy: it's just fun! Even if they are burning lights for me, for my tomorrow! I do not read Avloni, Tavallo, Siddiqi and Hakimzada. They are the ones who put me in this situation!..."

The critic writes that he defends himself from his article: "I think that today it is not possible to agree with this conclusion of Chulpan - since each of our classicists has a unique image, a style that differs from each other, their perception of the world and the world it is proved that they do not repeat each other in terms of their views and aesthetic principles. But Chulpan called them "the same, the same, the same!" as he is evaluating, he may be referring to some unique qualities of Eastern poetry. It seems that Ozod Sharafiddinov did not just study Chulpan's work. He analyzed not only Chulpan's poetry, prose, drama, but also his articles. Because these sources served as stepping stones to our understanding of Chulpan.

In general, Ozod Sharafiddinov tries to discover Chulpan's work on the basis of artistic rather than ideological. Munaqqid tries to evaluate Chulpan objectively. Chulpan's thinking, at that time he managed to determine the best balance between East and West, was his achievement, and Ozad Sharafiddinov carefully studies these achievements. In particular, his critical views on his poetry are discovering novelties in his prose. Ozod Sharafiddinov, as a Chulpan scholar, has been engaged in publishing and promoting Chulpan's works for years. The School of Chulpan Studies, started by Ozod Sharafiddinov, is currently being continued by literary scholars Dilmurod Kuronov and Zamira Eshonova. Literary scholar Umarali Normatov reported in his articles that Ozad Sharafiddinov went to the auditoriums and promoted the works of Chulpan and did a great job in understanding and interpreting Chulpan.

Ozod Sharafiddinov, as the leader of Chulpan scholars, deeply understood and deeply explained Chulpan's spirit, the conflicts of the complicated era, and the desire for freedom in the poet's heart. We hope that these processes in Chulpan studies, that is, researching his works, comparing literary texts, finding his poems from various periodicals, and researching Chulpan's work, will continue the courageous work started by Ozod Sharafiddinov.

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